

The Casework Effectiveness Scale- CES-10

Item no.	Item	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1.	The casework process helped me identify my problems.					
2.	The casework process helped me solve my problems.					
3.	The casework process helped me understand myself.					
4.	The casework process helped me gain self-confidence.					
5.	The casework process helped me learn to respect myself.					
6.	The casework process has helped me become a better person.					
7.	The casework process has helped identify the weak areas in my personality.					
8.	The casework process has helped improve my personality.					
9.	The casework process has helped me gain resources that I can use to solve problems in the future.					
10.	The casework process has helped me gain the ability to solve problems in the future.					

Scoring: Strongly agree: 4; Agree: 3; Neither agree nor disagree: 2; Disagree: 1; Strongly disagree: 0.

Maximum score: 40 and **Minimum score:** 0. Higher scores indicate higher levels of casework effectiveness. **Levels:** 0-12: Low, 13-25: Moderate, and 26 and above: High.

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